

Potability of water in Asansol coalfield rural areas : Chemical and biological studies

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Abstract : The investigation was undertaken with an objective of developing techniques for the potability of drinking water of some villages near the Asansol Coal field areas. For this investigation the water samples of different villages have been collected at pre-monsoon and post-monsoon seasons. In chemical analysis, the pH value, total hardness, total dissolved solid (TDS), total suspended solids (TSS), total solid presence, conductivity, different metal content (like arsenic, lead, copper, cadmium, iron etc.), chloride content etc. have been determined. In bacteriological analysis, the content of faecal coliform/*E. coli* have been determined. It was found from the chemical analysis that surface water is better for drinking purpose than ground water. Bacteriological studies also support the non-potability of ground water present in most of the villages.

Keywords : Potability, Asansol, coal-field area, chemical, *E. coli*.

Introduction

In the last few decades, increasing urbanization, cultivation and industrialization have caused enormous microbiological and chemical pollution of surface as well as ground waters. Microbiological contamination is mainly due to the discharge of sewage with faecal wastes of homotherms containing pathogenic microbes responsible for a variety of water borne diseases. The presence of certain group of aquatic bacteria, particularly conforms and faecal coliforms, indicate the possible contamination of water with pathogenic bacteria¹. Disposal of industrial effluents containing heavy metals into water sources is a major anthropogenic factor, responsible for metal pollution in various aquatic environments².

Water quality in the vicinity of abandoned mine sites may be significantly degraded as a result of ground and surface water by acid mine drainage³. This contamination is by metal compounds in dissolved and suspended form⁴. Investigations have also been made of the extent of heavy metal pollution of surface water, groundwater, soils, air and vegetation by mining and associated industrial activities, particularly thermal power plants and opencast coal mines⁵. Asansol is also one of the most

important coalmine rich industrial towns of Burdwan District of the state of West Bengal. The number of underground and opencast coalmines in West Bengal is 81 and 12 respectively and in Asansol-Raniganj Coalfield area this number is 46 and 7 respectively⁶. The total number of people working in Asansol-Raniganj Coalfield area is one lakh fourteen thousand. Thus it cannot be denied that this vast coalfield area is the chief source of water pollution in Asansol and its adjacent areas.

In rural coalfield areas near Asansol, water pollution due to industrial wastes and sewage has been assuming menacing proportions. Rivers, ponds and wells have water which is unsafe for drinking purposes. Survey of Coalfield areas shows that people are mostly dependent on municipal supply water and tubewell water. It is well known that water borne pathogens cause many diseases. Therefore, the supply water has to be checked from the microbiological point of view.

The waste water in coal mining area have different types of pollution like acidity due to formation of acidic mine water when pyrites (FeS_2) and other sulphide minerals are exposed to atmosphere because of mining operation. The problem is associated with underground min-

ing of high sulphur coals. High levels of dissolved solids are common in mine effluents. High levels of suspended solid and hardness in water is quite common in mine water. Chemical oxygen demand (COD) may be high and dissolved O₂ level may be low.

Regarding the potability of water in coalfield rural areas, the present investigation was undertaken with the object of shedding some light on the nature of drinking water used by the rural people of coalfield areas near some adjacent areas of Asansol Municipal Corporation and Panchayats.

Results and discussion

The potability of water demands that it must be more or less free from turbidity, colour, taste and odour (Table 3), well aerated and, most important of all, it must be free from pathogenic microorganisms and harmful chemicals. The samples were collected at two seasons, February-March 2010 (pre-monsoon) and August-September (post-monsoon) from different eight villages.

Water quality parameters :

Following water quality parameters were analysed.

Colour : No colour is found for all water samples. The presence of colour in drinking water is not directly related to health. Colour in drinking water may be due to the presence of coloured organic substances. If colour found in drinking water it is considered that the source is possibly unsafe and consumers may turn to alternative. But in all types of water samples no colour is found. So it can be concluded that those sources of drinking water are safe with respect to colour.

Total solid, dissolved solid and total suspended solid : The experimental result of total solid concentrations, dissolved solid concentrations and suspended solid concentrations in two different seasons are given in Tables 1A and 1B. These tables indicate that the amount of suspended substances are higher than the dissolved substances. It also gives the information that in ground water samples the amount of substances are much more higher than the surface water samples. The tables also show that the amount of all types of substances are too much high in 'Bartoria' ground water and 'Chelod' ground water sample. Among the different kinds of solid mainly total dissolved solid present in the drinking water is important. Water

with high dissolved solids has inferior palatability and may reduce the unfavorable physiological reaction in the transient consumer⁷. Solids at higher levels create excessive hardness, poor taste, mineral deposition and corrosion may occur. In the result it was observed that in all ground water samples the amount of all types of solids is high though not crossed the limiting value (Table 3). It was also observed that solid substances present in sample in undissolved condition with very high concentration, so it will be remove easily by simple filtration or sedimentation.

pH : The water samples exhibited an alkaline pH in the range of 7.05 to 9.46 (Tables 1A and 1B). Only three samples 'Chotodighari' surface water, 'Kalajaria' surface water and 'Kalajaria' ground water showing the pH 6.85, 6.90, 6.90 respectively. No significant difference was noted in the observed pH, the variation in pH due to change in sampling location was also insignificant. Only higher pH values were observed in samples collected during August-September, 2010. An acceptable range of pH of drinking water is from 6.5 to 8.5. Water with a pH below 6.5 is considered acidic and may cause heavy metal leaching⁸ causing plumbing damage etc. In all water samples the pH lying in the limited range.

Conductivity : The results of conductance in different water samples listed in Tables 1A and 1B. Like solid substances the conductance values are also high in all ground water samples compared to surface water samples. Again, it was observed that these values are high in the samples collected from post-monsoon season. But the values are very high in 'Chelod' ground water sample. Conductivity measurements offer a rapid and non-destructive way to measure ion content in the sample. High conductance values also cause many diseases⁹. The conductance values are showing a limiting range in respect of presence of ions which also supports the TDS result. Only in 'Chelod' ground water the value of conduction highly indicate presence of high amount of ions.

Total hardness : The results of total hardness in water sample are shown in Tables 1A and 1B. The tables indicate that the value of total hardness of ground water samples in two seasons are remarkably high. No significant difference also found in the samples collected at different seasons. The values of total hardness also indicate the heavy amount of dissolved substance in drinking wa-

Table 1A. Chemical analysis of water collected from pre-monsoon season

Sl. no.	Sample name	Color	Total solid (mg/L)	Total dissolved solid (mg/L)	Total undissolved solid (mg/L)	pH	Conductivity (μ s)	Hardness (mg/L)	Fe (mg/L)	Zn (μ g/L)	Cd (μ g/L)	Pb (μ g/L)	Cu (μ g/L)	Cl (mg/L)	As (mg/L)
1.	Bartoria - surface water	Colorless	1300	83.3	1216.7	7.05	120	60	20	34.78	34.51	8.97	13.06	74.5	Negative
2.	Bartoria - ground water	Colorless	28500	542	27958.0	7.35	660	280	22	71.79	37.68	9.34	13.32	12.8	Negative
3.	Chotodighari - surface water	Colorless	1000	88.5	911.5	6.85	135	56	20	30.77	32.46	7.95	12.30	102.3	Negative
4.	Chotodighari - ground water	Colorless	1500	423	1077	7.32	490	296	50	38.16	38.65	7.99	13.34	135	Negative
5.	Kalajaria - surface water	Colorless	1000	146	854	6.90	220	100	20	29.37	36.41	8.30	11.94	92	Negative
6.	Kalajaria - ground water	Colorless	3200	735	2465	6.90	805	440	22	56.64	38.42	10.17	12.39	220	Negative
7.	Dhenua - surface water	Colorless	800	150	650	7.20	225	92	50	33.21	33.08	8.48	16.58	84.2	Negative
8.	Dhenua - ground water	Colorless	2200	775	1425	7.26	415	476	70	38.69	37.02	8.70	16.93	156.3	Negative
9.	Tirat - surface water	Colorless	4600	149	4451	7.77	200	84	25	36.90	8.54	7.27	9.48	135	Negative
10.	Tirat - ground water		900	299	601	7.71	900	152	18	63.97	12.98	10.32	17.23	258	Negative
11.	Nuni - surface water	Colorless	3200	336	2864	8.11	700	60	20	34.91	33.99	7.88	11.40	114	Negative
12.	Nuni - ground water	Colorless	3400	77	3323	7.78	100	294	22	67.81	34.15	8.72	17.02	196.5	Negative
13.	Chelod - surface water	Colorless	5400	147	5253	7.64	200	84	16	41.90	1.36	7.27	12.34	95.6	Negative
14.	Chelod - ground water	Colorless	77400	741	76659	7.47	1600	440	22	423.28	386.02	35.07	29.54	496	Negative
15.	Asanbani - surface water	Colorless	5700	118	5582	7.68	100	58	20	67.81	33.41	8.43	11.36	71	Negative
16.	Asanbani - ground water	Colorless	2300	257	2043	7.98	600	224	20	71.46	51.73	8.53	11.87	92	Negative

Table 1B. Chemical analysis of water collected from post-monsoon season

Sl. no.	Sample name	Color	Total solid (mg/L)	Total dissolved solid (mg/L)	Total undissolved solid (mg/L)	pH	Conductivity (μ s)	Hardness (mg/L)	Fe (mg/L)	Zn (μ g/L)	Cd (μ g/L)	Pb (μ g/L)	Cu (μ g/L)	Cl (mg/L)	As (mg/L)
1.	Bartoria - surface water	Colorless	400	76.8	323.2	7.53	11	760	26	38.62	32.14	6.32	12.56	35.5	Negative
2.	Bartoria - ground water	Colorless	2000	799	1201	7.79	1226	500	32	78.91	46.32	14.26	14.26	248	Negative
3.	Chotodighari - surface water	Colorless	300	87.2	212.8	7.35	138	60	24	32.42	31.54	7.55	12.56	71	Negative
4.	Chotodighari - ground water	Colorless	600	376	224	8.12	560	240	42	37.12	33.52	8.01	12.98	142	Negative
5.	Kalajaria - surface water	Colorless	300	131	169	7.79	203	100	26	30.18	34.17	7.42	10.24	106.4	Negative
6.	Kalajaria - ground water	Colorless	700	520	180	8.25	797	330	24	55.21	39.84	11.28	13.26	214	Negative
7.	Dhenua - surface water	Colorless	400	131.7	268.3	7.99	202	110	48	31.49	36.56	7.84	14.26	71	Negative
8.	Dhenua - ground water	Colorless	500	137.9	362.1	8.17	212	130	52	45.74	37.45	7.92	15.10	106.4	Negative
9.	Tirat - surface water	Colorless	200	129.8	70.2	7.96	199	130	26	28.14	9.65	5.62	8.54	106.4	Negative
10.	Tirat - ground water	Colorless	1000	645	355	7.59	990	310	20	74.12	18.56	9.84	16.32	214	Negative
11.	Nuni - surface water	Colorless	1100	161	939	9.46	248	70	28	62.14	38.22	21.23	12.32	71	Negative
12.	Nuni - ground water	Colorless	1300	385	915	8.36	588	280	28	71.48	40.36	24.24	14.84	71	Negative
13.	Chelod - surface water	Colorless	1000	139	861	8.00	214	110	22	42.60	5.32	6.89	13.26	106.4	Negative
14.	Chelod - ground water	Colorless	4000	1161	2839	7.89	178	1790	20	365.14	401.23	34.52	30.26	319	Negative
15.	Asanbani - surface water	Colorless	1000	402	598	8.16	508	300	30	42.14	48.52	10.32	13.28	71	Negative
16.	Asanbani - ground water	Colorless	6000	330	5670	8.01	619	340	24	98.32	54.26	11.54	14.10	71	Negative

Table 2. Bacteriological analysis of water

Sl. no.	Sample	Sample collected from pre-monsoon season (February-March)				Sample collected from pre-monsoon season (August-September)							
		Presumptive test (No. of 5 tubes giving a positive reaction)		Confirmed test (MPN index/100 ml)	Membrane filter test (No. of coliforms in 100 ml)	IMViC test (both bacteria present)	Presumptive test (No. of 5 tubes giving a positive reaction)		Confirmed test (MPN index/100 ml)	Membrane filter test (No. of coliforms in 100 ml)	IMViC (both bacteria present)		
		10 ml 1 ml	0 ml 0.1 ml				10 ml 1 ml	0 ml 0.1 ml					
1.	Dhenua - ground water	5	5	0	130	36	Positive	5	3	1	75	44	Positive
2.	Dhenua - surface water	0	0	0	0	4	Positive	2	1	0	4	16	Positive
3.	Kalajharia - ground water	5	5	1	350	72	Positive	5	4	0	130	90	Positive
4.	Kalajharia - surface water	0	0	0	0	4	Positive	1	0	0	2	0	Positive
5.	Chotodighari - ground water	5	5	5	345	60	Positive	5	5	5	175	110	Positive
6.	Chotodighari - surface water	2	0	0	4	2	Positive	1	0	0	2	0	Positive
7.	Bartoria - ground water	5	4	2	38	32	Positive	5	5	5	32	64	Positive
8.	Bartoria - surface water	2	0	0	4	2	Positive	1	0	1	2	2	Positive
9.	Tirat - ground water	5	5	2	540	14	Positive	5	4	3	220	10	Positive
10.	Tirat - surface water	1	0	1	4	2	Positive	2	1	0	5	0	Positive
11.	Chelod - ground water	5	5	0	240	44	Positive	5	5	5	210	60	Positive
12.	Chelod - surface water	0	0	0	0	0	Positive	0	0	0	0	0	Positive
13.	Nuni - ground water	0	0	0	0	0	Positive	1	0	0	2	6	Positive
14.	Nuni - surface water	0	0	0	0	2	Positive	1	0	0	2	0	Positive
15.	Asanbani - ground water	0	0	0	0	0	Positive	3	3	0	0	2	Positive
16.	Asanbani - surface water	0	0	0	0	0	Positive	1	0	0	0	6	Positive

ter. It is recommended that water from any source is not always fit for consumption unless treated for hardness¹⁰. The observed results also support the TDS result and conductivity result. The total hardness value also does not cross the permissible limit (Table 3).

Metal content : Metal content values are listed in Tables 1A and 1B. Amount of iron is more or less identical in different localities at different seasons. It is observed that in all water samples iron content is very high (Table 3). Iron in water can be attributed to the weathering of rocks and minerals, acid mine drainage, landfill leachates, sewage effluents and iron related industries. Long time consumption of drinking water with high concentration of iron can lead to liver diseases¹¹.

amount is too much high. No significant values of cadmium content found in all water samples. Tested experiment in 'Chelod' ground water sample where cadmium content are indicating a very high value. There is no significant difference of lead content in all water samples. Again in 'Chelod' ground water sample this amount is too much high. There is no significant difference of copper content in all water sample except in all 'Chelod' ground water samples where it is high. The arsenic test gives the information that in the water samples either arsenic is not present or present in permissible range (Tables 1A and 1B). The mercuric bromide stain method proved that arsenic content in all samples did not crossed the limit i.e. 0.05 mg/L. In measurement of the metals content it was found that the amount of all metals were

Table 3. Indian standard specifications for drinking water IS : 10500

Sl. no.	Parameter	Requirement desirable limit	Remarks
1.	Colour (Hazen units)	5	May be extended upto 50 if toxic substances are suspected
2.	Turbidity NTU	10	May be relaxed upto 25 in the absence of alternate
3.	pH	6.5 to 8.5	May be relaxed upto 9.2 in the absence
4.	Total hardness (mg/L)	300	May be extended upto 600
5.	Copper (mg/L)	0.05	May be relaxed upto 1.5
6.	Iron (mg/L)	0.3	May be extended upto 1
7.	Manganese (mg/L)	0.1	May be extended upto 0.5
8.	Chlorides (mg/L)	250	May be extended upto 1000
9.	Sulphates (mg/L)	150	May be extended upto 400
10.	Nitrates (mg/L)	45	No relaxation
11.	Fluoride (mg/L)	0.6 to 1.2	If the limit is below 0.6 water should be rejected, Max. limit is extended to 1.5
12.	Mercury (mg/L)	0.001	No relaxation
13.	Cadmium (mg/L)	0.01	No relaxation
14.	Arsenic (mg/L)	0.05	No relaxation
15.	Lead (mg/L)	0.1	No relaxation
16.	Zinc (mg/L)	5.0	May be extended upto 10.0
17.	Chromium (mg/L)	0.05	No relaxation
18.	Odour	Unobjectionable	-
19.	Taste	Agreeable	-
20.	Dissolved solids (mg/L)	500	2000
21.	Suspended solids (mg/L)	600	-

The high concentration of metal in drinking water has many other adverse effects^{12,13}. The results were indicating that ground water samples zinc content is high (Tables 1A and 1B). But in 'Chelod' ground water sample this

present within the permissible limit except that in 'Chelod' ground water where the metal content is too much high.

Chloride content : The result of chloride content for all water samples is given in Tables 1A and 1B. The

values of chloride content in all ground water samples are high in comparison to surface water samples. Same trend is also observed in all sample collected in different seasons. The presence of chloride salts in drinking water in small amounts may not hurt us, but chloride by-products can do it. High concentration of chloride can form different by-product when mixed with organic matter. Except 'Chelod' ground water in all other water samples the chloride content is within the permissible limit (limiting range in drinking water is 250 mg/L).

Bacteriological analysis of water :

Bacteriological analysis of water was done to differentiate the coliform group by presumptive, confirmed and completed tests. After performing these tests with positive results; further investigation was required to know the presence of *E. coli* or *Enterobacter aerogenes* by using IMViC test.

Presumptive test : Presumptive test was done to confirm whether collected water samples contain lactose fermenting gas producing bacteria or not. The water samples collected during pre-monsoon season from different villages were subjected to presumptive test and most of the water samples showed positive results. Whereas some ground water samples and surface water samples showed negative results (Table 2). Ground water samples from all the villages gave positive result i.e. gas formation in the samples collected at post-monsoon season. Some surface water samples showed positive result also due to turbidity of river water after rainy season.

Confirmed coliform test : This test is used to confirm the presence of coliforms and to determine the MPN (Most probable number) value in water samples showing positive or doubtful presumptive test. When water collected at pre-monsoon season the ground water from all the villages showed positive confirmed test and MPN value ranges from 38 to 540. But ground water from 'Nuni' and 'Asabani' showed negative confirmed tests. The surface water from the entire villages gave negative confirmed test except 'Chotodighari', 'Bortoria' and 'Tirat', though these three villages gave very low MPN index (Table 2). Similar trend was observed when ground water samples collected at post-monsoon season but MPN index is low as compared to pre-monsoon season in all the villages. Surface water from all the villages showed

positive confirmed tests except 'Chelod' and 'Asabani' but MPN index was very low.

Completed coliform test and detection of coliforms using membrane filter method : By the experiment of completed coliform test and membrane filter method it was observed that at pre-monsoon season the ground water of all the eight villages except 'Tirat' shows large numbers of coliforms but surface water of all villages have fewer numbers of coliforms than ground water. Whereas the ground water of 'Nuni' and 'Asabani', coliforms are absent (Table 2). The results of the experiments done at post-monsoon season indicates that the ground water of all the villages showed same trend but the number of coliforms were more than the previous results (Table 2) except 'Tirat' village. The surface water also showed same trend. The ground water of 'Nuni' and 'Asabani' contain some coliforms.

IMViC tests : The results of IMViC tests indicate that the water collected from eight villages contains both types of bacteria (*E. coli* bacterium and *Enterobacter aerogenes* bacteria).

Potable water quality criteria : Quality criteria of water for drinking purposes have been prescribed by various authorities like World Health Organization (WHO), Indian Standards Institution (ISI) and Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR) etc. Besides the chemical and physical criteria, these authorities have prescribed bacteriological standards for water as well.

World Health Organization's guidelines for drinking water regarding bacteriological contents have been adopted by India.

WHO guidelines for drinking water points out the following criteria :

- (a) Total coliforms : Zero per 100 ml sample (0/100 ml).
Not more than 5% of samples should be positive.
The positive samples analysed for *E. coli* or faecal coliforms.
- (b) *E. coli* : Zero per 100 ml sample (0/100 ml)
- (c) Faecal coliform : Zero per 100 ml sample (0/100 ml)

The total numbers of coliform test result are reported in number of colonies per 100 ml.

The coliform test of ground water from different vil-

lages shows positive result during presumptive test and in most of the cases those results are confirmed. In IMViC test, the presence of *E. coli* and *Enterobacter aerogenes* were confirmed. The MPN index¹⁴ of ground water has been found to be higher than surface water. This indicates that surface water is potable but ground water is not fit for drinking. During post-monsoon period the MPN index is higher than that in winter period. This is due to the chance of contamination of water which is greater in rainy season than winter season. Village people use surface water throughout the year. The ground water is used for drinking purposes by most of the people of these villages rarely throughout the year. They use it only when surface water supply is stopped for 2–3 days due to some reasons. The surface water before supply through pipelines is treated, so there is very low or no chances of contamination. The ground water used by the villagers of 'Nuni' and 'Asabani' is fit for drinking because MPN index is two in only one case and coliforms are absent because the ground water is a closed system and there is less chance of contamination from outside. As the water of ground comes out through the layers of soil, it undergoes filtration which removes suspended particles, including microorganisms.

Experimental

Chemical analysis :

For colour test each sample was taken in a clean test tube and monitoring the colour visually in the presence of high intensity light. For determination of total solids 100 ml of the sample in a dry beaker was placed on an oven for evaporation to dryness at 103–105 °C. The beaker in a desiccator was cooled down and weighed. With the help of a digital TDS meter the amount of dissolved solid was measured directly. By these two values the amount of suspended solids easily determined. The pH values of different water samples were directly obtained by using a digital pH meter. The values of conductance of the different water sample read out using a digital conductivity meter. The hardness of water sample was determined using standard EDTA solution. Anodic stripping voltammetry was employed to find out the concentration of different metal ions in water solution. Measurements were carried out using Voltammetry-Amperometry Trace Analysis technique by standard addition procedure

using hanging mercury drop electrode (HMDE) as working electrode, Ag/AgCl, KCl (3 M solution) as reference electrode and large area carbon as counter electrode in an inert atmosphere by purging pure grade N₂ gas. The amount of chloride present in the water sample was determined by the titration with standard silver nitrate solution. Presence of permissible range of arsenic in water solution was tested by Mercuric Bromide stain method.

Biological test :

Presumptive coliforms test : Lactose fermentation tubes were inoculated with different water volumes and production of acid and gas from the fermentation of lactose in any of the tubes was a presumptive evidence of coliforms in the water sample :

Confirmed coliforms test : This test was used to confirm the presence of coliforms and to determine the MPN value in water samples showing positive or doubtful presumptive test. In the confirmed test, water samples from all the positive presumptive lactose broth tubes were inoculated into tubes of brilliant green lactose bile broth and inoculated at 35° for 48 h.

Completed coliforms test : EMB agar plates were streaked from positive tubes with a sterile inoculating loop. Inoculated plates were incubated at 35 °C for 24 h in an inverted position. After 24 h the inoculated plates were observed to detect coliform colonies.

Membrane filter method : In the membrane filter method, a water sample was passed through a thin sterile membrane filter (cellulose nitrate), diameter 47 mm which was kept in a special filter apparatus contained in a suction flask. The filter disc that contains the trapped microorganisms is aseptically transferred to a sterile Petridis having an absorbent pad saturated with a selective, differential liquid medium, and the colonies which develop following incubation are counted.

IMViC test of enteric bacteria : The IMViC tests consist of four different tests : (i) indole production, (ii) methyl red, (iii) Voges-Proskauer and (iv) citrate utilization. The IMViC tests were designed to differentiate Gram-negative bacilli (Family : Enterobacteriaceae) particularly *Escherichia coli* and the *Enterobacter-Klebsiella* group, on the basis of their biochemical properties and enzymatic reaction in the presence of specific substrates.

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